

A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO ATHLETIC TRAINING IS THE KEY TO SUCCESS

Dusyarov Toraboy Beknazarovich

Lecturer at the Termiz State University

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7874787>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th April 2023

Accepted: 27th April 2023

Online: 28th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Athletics, athlete, sports results, running, competition, Middle and long distance runners.

ABSTRACT

This article explains that the correct organization of athletics training is the key to success. Usually, 5-7 years of properly structured training brings a runner to high sports results. It is explained that achieving a good result depends on how developed the physical qualities of the runner are.

Success in running in athletics mainly depends on the optimal functioning of all organs and systems of the athlete. For this, first of all, the activity of the cardiovascular, respiratory and central nervous systems should be good.

Usually, 5-7 years of properly structured training brings a runner to high sports results. Achieving a good result depends on how developed the physical qualities of the runner are.

General and specific endurance play an especially big role in improving the level of training of a runner of different distances in athletics. Special endurance allows not only to maintain an average speed during the entire distance, but also to use accelerations based on the tactical plan.

Achieving high results in running different distances also depends on the level of maximum speed in sprinting. The best middle distance runners can run 100 m in 10.5 - 11.00 seconds, and long distance runners can run faster than 12 seconds. This allows them to maintain a high average speed throughout the distance. In addition, runners with high speed outperform other runners in acceleration at the finish line, even if their endurance is equal to others.

Speed alone is not enough for success. The amplitude of movements during running is very large. Therefore, only if the leg muscles of the runner are very strong and the joints are well-mobilized, he can take a long step and run easily. Therefore, it is necessary to perform various exercises that increase leg muscle strength and flexibility.

It is also necessary to educate the "feeling of speed", the ability to determine one's own speed based on one's subjective feelings (proprioceptive, visual, auditory).

More repetitive, variable, flat, and control techniques are used to increase running speed and endurance.

In the following years, a type of variable method called fartlek (running game) began to be used more. In a fartlek, irregular accelerations are performed and their speed and distance

can vary. Acceleration sometimes alternates with slow running, sometimes even fast running. Fartlek is mainly performed in open spaces, with groups and individually (32).

Currently, serial runs are widely used. For example: after 3-4 x300 m, 200 meters are run slowly (series), after which a few minutes of rest: walking or jogging very slowly. There can be several such series. They can be the same or different in terms of the length of the distance and the speed of running this distance.

A control run is held a few days or a week before the competition in order to see the runner's level of training and ability to distribute power over the distance.

Such running is usually conducted at a shorter distance than the training distance (for example, 600 m for 800 m runners, 1200 m for 1500 m runners, 3000 m for 5000 m runners; control running distance for women running 400 m - 300 m).

Both the runner's competition and the control run are equally good tools for improving performance.

Middle and long distance runners usually compete in multiple distances, but each runner should train for one distance. Which distance to consider as the main one depends on the athlete's wishes and his individual characteristics. For example, tall athletes whose speed in 100 m is more stable can be advised to specialize in middle distance running.

Currently, the so-called interval method is used in foreign countries for the training of middle and long-distance runners. This is similar to our variable method in that it is necessary to take into account the unique physiological and biochemical characteristics of each runner at this distance. For example, middle-distance runners need to increase their ability to use anaerobic (in response to the lack of pure oxygen for consumption) reaction energy, while long-distance runners need to increase their breathing capacity.

Middle- and long-distance runners repeat shorter distances less often than stayers. But their speed is much higher than the speed of stayers.

Each of the middle and long-distance runners should correctly define such sections, how many of them there should be, the speed at which they should be run, how long and how to rest between these sections. These factors determine the size of the load and its benefits.

You can't get a training load in the same order from training to training, as well as from week to week. In the weekly cycle, the amount of training should be sometimes more and sometimes less. The total weekly load increases for 2-3 weeks, and then decreases relatively ("wavy" training load for one week is somewhat lighter).

During the preparation period, the participants train 4 times a week, sometimes in the open air and sometimes in the hall. Until the start of the spring phase of training, they train in the hall no more than 2 times a week.

Classes last 1.5-2 hours in the gym and 2 hours in the open air. In some classes, it is possible to train in the open air first, and then in the hall. It is necessary to prepare the ground for summer achievements in the winter. Therefore, it is necessary to perform a very large amount of work at low and medium speed.

During the preparatory period (autumn-winter training), general and special preparatory exercises are in the main place. They are performed without shells or with shells (bells, bars, horizontal bars, ropes, rings, gymnastic wall) and with shells (dumbbells, barbells, balls, ropes, etc.). By doing exercises such as jumping, jumping, jumping over shells and

natural obstacles, running or walking with hips raised high, and running while forcing the leg to straighten when squatting, the muscles of the legs special attention is paid to strengthening.

During training, runners should also consider developing flexibility. For this purpose, many exercises with a large amplitude are performed, such as the following; standing next to the gymnastic wall and shaking legs; spreading the legs wide, swinging while sitting on the floor, etc. Some training sessions can consist only of general development and special exercises.

At the beginning of the autumn-winter preparatory stage of training, walking is used as a means of getting used to the increasingly frequent work (especially for beginners). At this stage, a walk at the same speed is also held (up to 1 hour for middle-distance runners, and up to 1.5 hours for long-distance runners). Moving from a steady run to a variable run, the faster sections are getting longer at the expense of the slower sections being shortened. Variable running in a certain ratio (for example, 4 minutes slow + 1 minute fast running 10-15 times), depending on the desire and mood of the runner (for example, 4 minutes slow + 1 minute fast + 2 minutes slow + 1 minute fast + 1 minute slow) can be transferred. Some runners sometimes run slowly and sometimes fast, not taking into account the time, but depending on their mood. When fatigue begins (there is no desire to run at the previous speed, the legs become "heavy", breathing becomes faster, etc.), the athlete switches from fast running to slow running.

In order to develop general and special endurance, cross-country is always important, and especially during the training period. Cross-country is held both in autumn (outside the city, in the forest, in parks) and in winter (on snow-covered paths, on snow).

Because the conditions in open areas are changing, the athlete can tolerate more stress there than when running in constant conditions.

References:

1. Shokirjonova K.T. Yengil atletika (musoba qa qoidalari). O'quv qo'llanma. T., Lider Press, 2017. 352 b.
2. Quدراتov R. Q. Sakrash texnikasi asoslari. Studentlarning mustaqil ishi uchun problematik ma'ruza. T., O'zDJTI, 2019. 26 b.
3. Quدراتov R. Q. Sportcha yurish va yugurish texnikasining asoslari. Talabalarning mustaqil ishlari uchun qo'llanma. T., O'zDJTI, 2020. 18 s.
4. Chorievna, D. Y., & Or'olovich, B. C. (2021). Opportunities to use national and movement games in physical education and athletics. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(05), 909-913.
5. Menglimurod O'g'li, E. E. (2021). Effectiveness and Advantages of using Pedagogical Technologies in Teaching Sports. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 92-94.
6. Urolovich, B. C. (2021). Features of the Methods used in Physical Education. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 88-91.

7. Ulaboyevich, B. G. . (2023). Increasing the Efficiency of the Methodology of Conducting Physical Education Lessons for Students of Grades 5-9 in Hot Climate Conditions. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(4), 137-140.
8. Ulobaevich, B. G. A. (2022). Natural Health Instructions in Organizing the Daily Life of School Students Efficiency of Use Reasonable Use in Physical Education. Miasto Przyszłości, 177-179.
9. Boboqulov, C. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(5), 147-149
10. O'ROLOVICH, C. B., & O'GLI, E. E. M. (2020). The Role and Effective Importance of Moving Games in the Development of the Physical Qualities of Athletes. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 7(10), 136-138.
11. Abduqahhorovich, S. H. (2022). INTERACTION OF SCHOOL AND FAMILY IN EDUCATION OF SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN. Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 4, 226-229.
12. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12).
13. Urolovich, B. C., & Panji o'g'li, A. S. (2022). JISMONIY MADANIYAT DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSIYON PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI. World scientific research journal, 4(2), 126-131.
14. Boboqulov, C. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING SKILLS TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(4), 113-116.
15. Tashmurotov, F. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 199-202.
16. Bobokulov Chori Urolovich, Zarina Rakhimova Fakhridin qizi. (2023). CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE FORMATION IN THE FAMILY. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 325-330
17. Eshkobilov Elmurod, Bobokulov Chori Urolovich. (2023). FACTORS DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 293-297.
18. Tashmurotov, F. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 199-202.
19. Bobokulov Chori Urolovich Eshkobilov Elmurod Menglimurod's Son. (2023). STANDARDS FOR CORRECT ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE EDUCATION STUDENTS. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 319-324.
20. Erikhonovich, T. F. (2022). Method of Organization Lessons of Physical Education in Secondary Schools. European journal of innovation in nonformal education, 2(3), 238-241.
21. Urolovich, B. C. . (2023). Scientific Effects of the Modular Approach in Teaching the Theory and Methodology of Physical Education. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(4), 141-144.
22. Abduqahhorovich, S. X. . (2023). Strength Training in Football Training. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(3), 138-141

23. Abdukahharovich, S. H. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF WRESTLING SPORTS FOR SOCIETY AND THE HISTORY OF ITS FORMATION. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 10, 312-316.

24. SHARIPOV, K. A. (2021). TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS OF ELEMENTARY CLASSES IN THE PROCESS OF STUDENTS STUDENTS PRACTICE. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (12), 1339-1343.